

Rheological Properties of Hagfish Intermediate Filament Protein (rHIF) Spinning Dopes

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Abstract

Understanding the rheological properties of spinning dopes is critical for fiber development, as viscosity directly influences spinnability, spinning parameters, and fiber mechanical properties. In this work, we focus on recombinant hagfish intermediate filament protein (rHIF), a biomimetic polymer engineered through recombinant expression in *E. coli* that offers an alternative to synthetic high-performance fibers. By characterizing the flow behavior of rHIF spinning dopes across various solvent systems, concentrations, and aging times, we aim to establish a robust protocol for protein fiber spinning. These viscosity measurements are essential for optimizing dopes for stable fiber formation and ensuring consistent performance in subsequent characterizations.

1. Materials and Methods

1.1. Materials

Recombinant hagfish intermediate filament protein (rHIF) was provided by Prof. Justin Jones (Utah State University). The protein was expressed in *E. coli*, purified, and shipped for use in these experiments. 1,1,1,3,3,3-Hexafluoro-2-propanol (HFIP; cat. 003409) was purchased from Oakwood Chemicals. Formic acid (FA; lab grade, 98%; cat. A0470831) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO, 1000 kg/mol, lot T291006) was used as a spinnability aid and was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

1.2. Preparation of rHIF spinning dopes

In the first part of the experiment, rHIF was dissolved at target concentrations (wt% w/v) in FA in a closed container for 2 hours at room temperature and allowed to sit for an hour after stirring to ensure full solvation and homogeneity. Two solutions—10 wt% rHIF and 15 wt% rHIF—were prepared to assess viscosity changes over time. In neat FA, rHIF dissolved readily with stirring, producing uniform, opaque, light brown solutions after 2 hours, though some foaming occurred at both concentrations (Figure 1).

Figure 1. rHIF protein in different solvents: 10 wt% rHIF in FA, 15 wt% rHIF in FA and 15% rHIF+PEO in 85:15 HFIP:FA (from left to right)

rHIF was also dissolved in an 85:15 HFIP:FA solvent system with stirring for 3 hours (magnetic stirrer, at 900 rpm) and allowed to sit for an hour to ensure full solvation and homogeneity. One solution—15 w/v % rHIF and 0.25 w/v% PEO—was prepared to assess the viscosity change. In this solvent system, rHIF dissolved readily with stirring, producing uniform, opaque, gray solutions after 3 hours (Figure 1).

All the solutions were stored at room temperature throughout the experiment.

PEO was incorporated into the formulation to improve the spinnability of the rHIF. For more information regarding electrospun rHIF fibers, refer to previous work from our team: [Electrospinning Hagfish Intermediate Filament Protein and Fabrication of Aligned Fiber Bundles](#).

1.3. Methods

The flow behavior of all rHIF spinning dopes was characterized at room temperature using an AMETEK Brookfield DVNext cone/plate rheometer (Model DVNXRVDBG) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: AMETEK Brookfield DVNext Cone/Plate Rheometer

For each measurement, the CPM-52Z spindle was used. The cone-plate gap was set to 0.0005 inch (0.013 mm) prior to each testing, and a sample volume of 0.5 mL was loaded directly in the center of the cup. The samples were allowed to rest for 60 seconds to relieve residual stresses before testing. Viscosity measurements were conducted across a range of shear rates, with the specific range chosen to maintain a torque reading between 10–100%. Two independent replicates were performed.

To assess the change in viscosity over time, separate aging studies were performed for each spinning dope, with aging time defined from the end of the initial stirring process:

- **10 wt% rHIF and 15 wt% rHIF in FA:** Viscosity was measured at 1 hour (1h), 24 hours (24h), 48 hours (48h), and 72 hours (72h).
- **15 wt% rHIF in FA:** Viscosity of this spinning dope also assessed short-term (at 1h, 2h, 3h, 4h, 5h, 6h, and 24h) to characterize initial structural changes.
- **15 wt% rHIF + 0.25 wt% PEO in 85:15 HFIP:FA:** Viscosity was measured at 1h, 3h, 5h, and 24h.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Rheological properties of 10 wt% and 15 wt% rHIF in formic acid over a 72-hour period

The flow behaviour of two spinning dopes—10 wt% rHIF and 15 wt% rHIF in FA—were characterized using a cone/plate rheometer. Figure 3 shows the viscosity change of the 10 wt% rHIF dope over a 72-hour period. The hagfish dope exhibited a non-Newtonian shear-thinning behaviour, where measured viscosity decreases as the shear rate increases. This shear-thinning behavior was only prominent immediately after dope preparation (1h) whereas it showed a Newtonian behavior after 24 hours.

Protein dopes at low concentrations might exhibit Newtonian behavior specifically at low shear rates. Further rheological characterization is required to fully elucidate the shift to Newtonian behavior observed in the 10 wt% rHIF solution.

Figure 3: The viscosity change of the 10 wt% rHIF in FA over a 72-hour period

As the spinning dope aged, we observed a significant decrease in viscosity. For instance, at a shear rate of 200 s^{-1} , the viscosity dropped from approximately 95–99 cP at 1 hour to approximately 70 cP at 24 hours.

After 24 hours, the viscosity stabilized at approximately 59 cP, remaining constant across different shear rates for samples aged for 24h, 48h, and 72h (Table 1). The most significant viscosity changes occurred within the initial 24 hours of aging, indicating rapid structural evolution of the protein solution during this period.

Table 1. The viscosity of 10 wt% rHIF in FA at different shear rates over a 72-hour period.

Shear Rate (s ⁻¹)	rHIF 10% 1h_1	rHIF 10% 1h_2	rHIF 10% 24h_1	rHIF 10% 24h_2	rHIF 10% 48h_1	rHIF 10% 48h_2	rHIF 10% 72h_1	rHIF 10% 72h_2
200	95.25	99.22	70.45	69.45	58.54	59.53	57.55	58.54
300	93.27	95.25	69.45	70.12	58.21	59.53	58.21	60.19
400	92.27	93.76	69.95	67.47	57.55	60.03	58.04	58.54
500	91.68	93.27	69.06	68.66	58.34	60.33	58.34	58.34

The 15% w/v solution was consistently much more viscous than the 10% w/v solution, as expected. Throughout the 72-hour period, the 15% concentration maintained a viscosity approximately 2.8 to 3.2 times higher than the 10% concentration. At a shear rate of 200 1/s (1h), the 15% w/v dope exhibited a mean viscosity of 273.9 cP, compared to 97.2 cP for the 10% w/v dope (Table 1 and Table 2). The 15% hagfish dope exhibited similar behavior, with a sharp decline in viscosity observed within the first 24 hours, suggesting structural changes or protein degradation in the formic acid solvent (Figure 4). Across all test conditions (1h, 24h, 48h, and 72h), the dope exhibited shear-thinning behavior.

Figure 4: The viscosity change of the 15 wt% rHIF in FA over a 72-hour period

As shown in Table 2, the viscosity continued to decrease after the 48-hour mark. Crucially, at this stage, the solution transitioned into a non-homogeneous, gel-like state, leading to a significant loss of reproducibility, a notable variability between the replicates. To improve reliability, additional replicates will be included in future work to strengthen the statistical validity of these findings.

Table 2. The viscosity of 15 wt% rHIF in FA at different shear rates over a 72-hour period.

Shear Rate (s ⁻¹)	rHIF 15% 1h_1	rHIF 15% 1h_2	rHIF 15% 24h_1	rHIF 15% 24h_2	rHIF 15% 48h_1	rHIF 15% 48h_2	rHIF 15% 72h_1
100	285.8	291.7	208.4	202.4	176.6	254	204.4
150	280.5	276.5	198.4	193.1	177.3	217	198.4
200	274.8	272.9	195.5	192.5	174.6	203.4	191.5
300	269.2	269.9	193.8	189.2	172.6	197.8	184.5
350	271.6	269.9	193.9	188.2	171.8	192.2	179.2
400	269.9	266.4	194.5	188	172.1	186.5	177.1
500	262.3	260	195.7	187.7	170.3	184.9	177.8

2.2. Rheological properties of 15 wt% rHIF in formic acid over a 24-hour period

To further define the optimal processing window, we characterized the viscosity change of the 15 wt% rHIF in FA spinning dope over the initial 6-hour period, which represents the practical timeframe for fiber spinning experiments. We also measured the viscosity of the solution after 24 hours. The spinning dope appeared rheologically stable between 1 and 6 hours, where viscosity fluctuations were minimal compared to the 24-hour drop (Figure 5).

Figure 5: The viscosity change of the 15 wt% rHIF in FA spinning dope over a 24-hour period

The first 1h replicate displayed an initially higher viscosity at low shear rates (up to 390.9 cP at 100 s⁻¹), but the viscosity profiles from all 1-to-6-hour measurements converged to similar values (ranging from 251.2 cP to 277.8 cP) at the high shear rate of 500 s⁻¹ (Table 3).

Replicate measurements at the 1-hour mark show the highest variability but variability improves dramatically after the first hour and for all other time points, the replicates remain consistently accurate regardless of the shear rate. Further investigation into this 1h measurement reproducibility requires increasing the number of replicates to enhance the statistical confidence of the measurements.

Table 3. The viscosity of 15 wt% rHIF in FA at different shear rates over a 24-hour period.

Shear Rate (s ⁻¹)	rHIF 15% 1h_1	rHIF 15% 1h_2	rHIF 15% 2h_1	rHIF 15% 2h_2	rHIF 15% 3h_1	rHIF 15% 3h_2	rHIF 15% 4h_1	rHIF 15% 4h_2	rHIF 15% 5h_1	rHIF 15% 5h_2	rHIF 15% 6h_1	rHIF 15% 6h_2	rHIF 15% 24h_1	rHIF 15% 24h_2
100	390.9	285.8	293.7	295.7	287.7	289.7	271.9	287.7	285.8	283.8	281.8	281.8	222.3	230.2
150	340	273.8	284.4	292.4	283.1	284.4	272.5	280.5	275.2	275.2	275.2	273.8	218.3	224.9
200	317.5	270.9	279.8	283.8	277.8	276.8	281.8	276.8	268.9	269.9	268.9	266.9	215.3	220.3
300	292.4	266.6	275.2	277.8	269.9	271.2	281.1	269.9	260.6	263.9	261.3	259.3	211	216.3
350	282.4	265.3	275.5	277.8	268.2	270.4	281.8	271.6	257.4	264.8	262.5	256.8	209.2	216
400	278.3	263.9	275.3	277.3	269.4	270.4	277.8	272.4	257	264.4	259	256	206.9	214.3
500	267.9	259.6	271.1	277.8	265.1	267.9	273.1	274.6	252	261.9	254.4	251.2	204.4	212.3

Consistent with previous measurements, the 15% rHIF dope exhibited pronounced shear-thinning behavior during the initial 6-hour period. Viscosity decreased significantly as the shear rate increased from 100 s⁻¹ to 500 s⁻¹.

Across all shear rates, the average viscosity gradually declined over time, dropping from 289.7 cP at 1 hour to 264.9 cP at 6 hours. At the highest applied shear rate of 500 s⁻¹, the viscosity remained stable between 263.7 and 256.9 cP during the first 5 hours.

2.3. Rheological properties of 15 wt% rHIF with PEO in HFIP:FA over a 24-hour period

We also characterized the flow behavior of hagfish dope prepared in an HFIP:FA solvent and how its viscosity evolves over a 24-hour period. The hagfish dope in this alternative solvent system also exhibited clear non-Newtonian, shear-thinning (pseudoplastic) behavior across all tested time points (Figure 6).

During the first 5 hours of the experiment, the spinning dope's viscosity remained relatively stable. The average viscosity at a low shear rate (60 s⁻¹) showed minimal fluctuation, staying within the range of 984 cP to 994 cP. This suggests that the solution's internal structure is largely maintained in the short term.

Figure 6: Viscosity change of 15 wt% rHIF with 0.25 wt% PEO in HFIP:FA (85:15) over a 24-hour period.

A pronounced increase in viscosity occurred between the 5-hour and 24-hour marks. After 24 hours, the average viscosity at 60 s^{-1} increased to 1114.5 cP—a ~13% increase from the 5-hour measurement (Table 4).

Table 4. The viscosity of 15 wt% rHIF with 0.25% PEO in HFIP:FA at different shear rates over a 24-hour period.

Shear Rate (s ⁻¹)	rHIF+PEO 15% 1h_1	rHIF+PEO 15% 1h_2	rHIF+PEO 15% 3h_1	rHIF+PEO 15% 3h_2	rHIF+PEO 15% 5h_1	rHIF+PEO 15% 5h_2	rHIF+PEO 15% 24h_1	rHIF+PEO 15% 24h_2
60	995.5	982.3	1009	979	939.3	1029	1078	1151
80	969.9	964.9	984.8	952.5	915.3	997.2	1059	1129
100	950.5	942.6	966.4	938.6	900.9	972.4	1044	1111
150	910.2	904.9	930	912.8	871.8	940.6	1005	1086
200	895	889	913.8	896	856.3	922.7	985.3	N/A

This hagfish dope exhibited an increase in viscosity after 24 hours while all the other dopes prepared in neat formic acid (FA) exhibited a decrease in viscosity.

As environmental stress such as heat and acid denatures the protein, and leads to a structural change such as unfolding into an elongated random coil. This uncoiling increases inter-molecular friction, leading to a rise in intrinsic viscosity. It is also expected for protein solutions to undergo denaturation (unfolding, aggregation) with

aging. This "aging" effect indicates that the hagfish dope may be undergoing structural transitions which increases its resistance to flow over time.

In addition to the HFIP:FA solvent system, the presence of 0.25% PEO polymer in this dope may affect the flow behavior. Future iterations of this experiment will incorporate larger sample sizes and different solvent ratios to further characterize the flow behavior of hagfish dopes.

3. Conclusion

In this work, we used a cone/plate rheometer to investigate the rheological properties of recombinant hagfish intermediate filament protein (rHIF) spinning dopes across a parameter space of solvents, concentrations, and aging times.

The rHIF dopes in neat formic acid exhibited a sharp decrease in viscosity within the first 24 hours, indicating a possible rapid structural evolution or degradation of the protein solution. The 10 wt% rHIF dope initially displayed a non-Newtonian behavior but transitioned to a Newtonian behavior after 24 hours, stabilizing at a viscosity of approximately 59 cP. The 15 wt% rHIF dope maintained a pronounced shear-thinning behavior and was consistently 2.8 to 3.2 times more viscous than the 10 wt% dope. However, this concentration transitioned into a non-homogeneous, gel-like state after 48 hours, resulting in significant loss of reproducibility. 15 wt% FA dope was rheologically stable between 1 and 6 hours, with minimal fluctuations, making this the optimal processing window.

In contrast to the FA dopes, the 15 wt% rHIF dope formulated with PEO in the 85:15 HFIP:FA solvent system showed a pronounced increase in viscosity after the 5-hour mark, rising by approximately 13% after 24 hours. This possible "aging" effect suggests the protein may be undergoing structural transitions, such as unfolding or aggregation, that increase resistance to flow in this specific solvent system.

In summary, for optimal reproducibility in fiber spinning, it is recommended to use the rHIF dopes within the stable 1-to-6-hour processing window. The gathered rheological data provides a defined starting point for optimizing rHIF dope formulations for consistent fiber formation.

4. Future directions

The data in this report provides a defined starting point for understanding the effect of protein concentration, solvent systems and aging time on the flow behavior of rHIF protein solutions. The future work will focus on increasing the number of replicates for rheology measurements to enhance experimental precision and running fiber spinning experiments to test the rheological properties of the spinning dopes on spinnability and fiber properties.

In addition, we plan to test the effect of storage conditions and continuous stirring (to sustain homogeneity) throughout the experiment. Future work will also include new characterization methods such as Gel Electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE), Raman

Spectroscopy and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Spectroscopy for protein stability determination over time.

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